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A Century of The Foursquare Gospel

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Pentecostal Education (formerly The Pentecostal Educator) semiannually e-publishes scholarly and practical articles related to theological education within the Pentecostal tradition to encourage the continuing maturation of Pentecostal theological education. It is intentionally practical, applied, and international.

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Foursquare Hispanics: Distinctives of a Growing Community within Foursquare

Hugo Aldana Jr. and Daniel Ruarte

Abstract

The centennial of the Foursquare church is a great opportunity to celebrate how God has been faithful within the Hispanic movement in the US and around the world. This paper attempts to look at the impact of Aimee Sample McPherson's ministry on the Hispanic community and present what we believe are outstanding distinctives of this beautiful group. First, it is a community that loves *la familia* (*family*), second, a community that is not ashamed of its Pentecostal identity, on the contrary, it emphasizes strong Pentecostal ministry, the praxis of spiritual gifts inside and outside the walls of the church, and the exercise of spiritual leadership. Thirdly, Foursquare Hispanics value biblical-theological education for leadership and, finally, we are a people faithful to *las tradiciones* (*traditions*). This writing is not exhaustive but seeks to reflect our identity. We are Foursquare Hispanics!

Keywords: Hispanic Pentecostal, Foursquare Hispanics, distinctives, ICFG

Introduction

In the centennial year of the International Church of the Foursquare Gospel (ICFG 1923-2023), we are pleased to share the legacy of the Hispanic community and how Foursquare values have allowed for unique Hispanic distinctives to be visible to the world. The Foursquare Hispanic movement has been growing since its inception. According to a report produced by the Hispanic Theological Association (ATH), formerly recognized as the Hispanic Association for Theological Education, the Foursquare Church in the United States in 1972 had a

total of ten Hispanic churches established in Southern California.¹ By 1993, this number grew to sixty in California and forty-two in other areas of the nation for an estimated total of 102 Hispanic churches.² In 2014, an article by then Hispanic district supervisor Juan Vallejo explained the continual growth in the Hispanic movement—216 Hispanic congregations.³

Today, the U.S. Hispanic National Foursquare District oversees 300 Hispanic congregations in the U.S., including Puerto Rico.⁴ This is only a small glimpse of a fruitful and growing community within Foursquare and does not include all the Spanish-speaking countries where Foursquare is established, which comprises all the *Foursquare Hispanics* around the world. We should celebrate this as part of Sister Aimee Semple McPherson’s legacy and the first 100 years of Foursquare ministry. Foursquare Hispanics is a growing community!

The Church of the Foursquare Gospel was born out of the Pentecostal movement of Azusa Street in 1906.⁵ The founder, Aimee Semple McPherson, embodying the DNA of the resulting revival and of the New Testament Church, was called by God to preach the gospel internationally and interdenominationally. The cosmopolitan city of Los Angeles was the epicenter from which the evangelistic movement began to take shape, and like Jerusalem on the Day of Pentecost (Acts 2), Los Angeles in 1906 was home to dozens of languages and cultures.⁶ Thus, before going to the nations, you only had to look at the thousands of immigrants in the city where Foursquare began. Among these different

¹ Wilson Rodelo, *Toward a History of the Hispanic Evangelical Church of Southern California* (Montebello: Hispanic Association for Theological Education, 1993), Figure #9.

² Nathaniel M. Van Cleave, *The Vine and the Branches: A History of the International Church of the Foursquare Gospel* (Lake Mary: Creation House, 1992), 83.

³ Juan Vallejo and Andy Butcher, “The Hispanic Quadrangular Movement Wins Altitude,” in *Foursquare Leaders* (Los Angeles: November 2014), 52.

⁴ Communication with the Hispanic National District administrator, August 2023.

⁵ Roberts Liardon, *The Azusa Street Revival* (Shippensburg: Destiny Image Publishers, 2006), 63-90, 197-200.

⁶ Since its founding in 1781, the city of “El Pueblo de Nuestra Señora la Reina de los Ángeles de Porziuncula,” better known as the city of Los Angeles, was erected as a metropolis with a diversity of cultures and languages. See *The History of Los Angeles*, LACITY.GOV, 2023, <https://lacity.gov/government/history-los-angeles>.

cultures and languages, Foursquare Hispanics surfaced from the beginning of Foursquare.

When the iconic Angelus Temple opened in January 1923, it was an English-speaking congregation, but by January 1925 work was established among Greeks, Armenians, Hispanics, Germans, and Japanese. A fruitful and cross-cultural ministry was reaching the city and county.⁴ Nathaniel M. Van Cleave notes that the heart of Sister McPherson and the early leaders of the movement emphasized efforts to reach non-Anglo groups as well, and Foursquare was perceived as a cross-cultural movement.⁵

As the demographics of the area where Angelus Temple was located became increasingly Hispanic in population, the Temple began to have regular services in Spanish. The first Hispanic department of the church was founded in 1928, having services entirely in the language of *Cervantes*. In 1929, all Hispanic parishioners were received as members of Angelus Temple, and it became widely known that Sister McPherson had Hispanics in her heart.⁶ In fact, it is said that she began using the term “Hispanic” decades before the U.S. government made it an official designation.⁷

In 1930, the first Foursquare Hispanic congregation apart from Angelus Temple began in the Los Angeles suburb of Canoga Park; it was followed shortly thereafter by a church in the neighboring city of San Gabriel, and slowly by other churches in cities throughout California. Many of those efforts were led by Sister McPherson’s

⁴ Jim Scott, *Hispanic Foursquare—Part 1*, https://resources.foursquare.org/foursquare_hispana_part_1/.

⁵ Van Cleave, *The Vine and the Branches*, 92.

⁶ Jim Scott, *Hispanic Foursquare—Part 2*, https://resources.foursquare.org/foursquare_hispana_part_2/.

⁷ The term Hispanic was used in a census by the United States government in the 1960s to identify all those who spoke Spanish. See, Cristina Lacomba, *Hispanics and/or Latinos in the United States* (Cervantes Observatory of Harvard University), <https://cervantesobservatorio.fas.harvard.edu/>. The term Hispanic comes from the word “Hispania,” the Latin term for Spain, and refers to everything that has to do with Spain geographically and linguistically. Thus, the Hispanic countries are those that speak Spanish, that is, most of Latin America and Spain, which adds up to twenty-two nations. See Nicole Canun, *The Powerful Role of Family in Hispanic Culture [Unlike U.S. Culture]*, Homeschool Hispanic Academy, <https://www.spanish.academy/blog/the-powerful-role-of-family-in-hispanic-culture-unlike-u-s-culture/>.

mother. The growth reflected Sister McPherson's passion for *the whole gospel to the whole world*. As Hispanic Foursquare churches began to flourish, both in the number of congregations and in its leaders establishing Bible schools to train Hispanic workers, increasing Hispanic immigration in California, Arizona, Nevada, and Texas led to Hispanic churches being planted outside of California.

From the beginning, Sister McPherson realized that advancing the Foursquare movement necessitated the establishment of a training school for those called to Foursquare ministry. The Echo Park Evangelistic and Missionary Training Institute later became the Lighthouse of International Foursquare Evangelism (LIFE), then LIFE Bible College, and today Life Pacific University (LPU).⁸ This educational and formative arm of the movement helped shape culture, create a tradition, and develop affiliation; for many years, it was the sole formative and developmental tool to prepare ministers for the denomination. LIFE Bible College also included cross-cultural elements that appealed to Spanish-speaking leaders and those with a call to missions in Spanish-speaking countries. By 1927, the Bible college was offering Spanish courses as part of the curriculum. As a result of these efforts, many graduates founded Hispanic churches both in California and other parts of the United States, and some were sent to other countries. For example, the first missionaries sent to a Spanish-speaking nation were the Edwards family; Rev. and Mrs. Edwards were LIFE Bible College graduates. They went to Panama in 1928. After twenty years of ministry in Panama, the Foursquare church grew to more than 100 congregations in the nation.⁹ This fruitful beginning of international ministry to Foursquare Hispanics was extraordinary.

As more and more early Foursquare missionaries were sent out, Sister McPherson always maintained an emphasis on missionaries to Latin America. In the U.S., the numerical growth of Hispanic churches necessitated that administrative divisions and districts had to be organized. With the same fervor that ministers were prepared at LIFE Bible College, Hispanics founded schools that have prepared many ministers around the U.S. and the world. The Foursquare tradition taught Hispanics the love for training and education, which, although much is still needed by way of training Hispanics, the Hispanic people have enthusiastically embraced the importance of education and training.

⁸ Van Cleave, *The Vine and the Branches*, 49.

⁹ Van Cleave, *The Vine and The Branches*, 97.

Since its founding, the Foursquare tradition has embodied traits that are akin to those in the Hispanic community and so it was not difficult to win their hearts. In addition to not being discriminated against, Hispanics were treated like family from the beginning, which is highly valued in Hispanic communities. Foursquare also fueled the migrant spirit of Hispanics, embodying in them the Foursquare DNA of a genuine love for the Master’s mission of evangelism to the whole world and the importance of going to other communities, regions, and countries to share the gospel.

Most recently, advances to promote and bless Foursquare Hispanics include establishing a nationwide Hispanic National District with the vision to reach first, second, and third-generation Hispanics.¹⁰ This strategic corporate decision was motivated by a desire to expand ministry to Foursquare Hispanics even more.

Distinctives of the Hispanic Foursquare Movement

Hispanic Foursquare is a community that loves *la familia* (family). As noted above, *familia* is of high value in the Hispanic community. Sister McPherson’s treatment of Hispanics as equals who were made to feel like family was a determining factor for the early growth of the Hispanic community within Foursquare. The fact that Hispanics were treated as *familia* allowed a greater connection and reach into the community. Angel Jordan (Director of Hispanic Initiatives at the Billy Graham Evangelistic Association) affirms that Hispanics are a cultural group who have a high value on personal relationships and that appreciation is greater when it comes to spiritual matters.¹¹ Canun, a leader within the Hispanic community, testifies that two fundamental values of the Hispanic people are *closeness* and *familiarity*, pointing out the fact that when it comes to the family, this is not understood to be just the nuclear family, but also the extended family.¹² It is common to see uncles, aunts, and grandparents involved in Hispanic homes along with the immediate members of the family.

¹⁰ *Meet Foursquare’s New District Supervisory Teams*, <https://resources.foursquare.org/meet-foursquares-new-district-supervisory-teams/>.

¹¹ Angel Jordán, *Eight Hispanic Values Every Church Must Keep in Mind*, Life Research, <https://research.lifeway.com/2023/03/23/8-hispanic-values-every-church-must-keep-in-mind/>.

¹² Canun, *The Powerful Role of Family in Hispanic Culture*.

As a result, Hispanics feel a moral responsibility to help other family members in need. Support and safety among the extended family are the backbone of the Hispanic family. Canun points out that this moral responsibility is a hallmark in the Hispanic community because of the support needed in trying to serve beyond their limits.¹³ When Sister McPherson sought to care for and serve families around the city, she allowed everyone equal access to the Angelus Temple Commissary, thus seeing to it that all families, including immigrant families, had their most basic needs covered during the Great Depression; Foursquare's earliest *cuidando de la familia* ("caring for the family") had a profound impact on Hispanics.

The Foursquare movement arose in a complex political and social time, yet flourished in ways that at times were counter-cultural.¹⁴ This resilience resonated with the Hispanic value of resilience seen in the effort to keep the family together. A study conducted in 2022 notes that "when faced with adversity, many Latino families rely on their strengths to provide a loving and nurturing environment for their children."¹⁵

Finally, Foursquare resonated with the Hispanic community in encouraging bilingualism and biculturalism, children's classes, work with youth, attention to adults, and, above all, proclaiming a message of hope—the Foursquare Gospel, a Christ-centered gospel that was proclaimed from every pulpit. Today, Hispanic Foursquare is a strong and healthy part of the Foursquare U.S. Church that emulates the movement's DNA through these same works and this same proclamation.

¹³ Canun, *The Powerful Role of Family in Hispanic Culture*.

¹⁴ For example, women still did not have a privileged place in pastoral ministry and socially they were not allowed to vote; yet, in that context, a great church movement that was initially built largely on women in leadership ministry began that has now impacted the world for 100 years. See Matthew A. Sutton, "Clutching to 'Christian' America: Aimee Semple McPherson, the Great Depression and the Origins of Pentecostal Activism," *Journal of Policy History* 17, no. 3 (July 2005): 308-338.

¹⁵ Nathasha Cabrera, Angelica Alonso, et al. *Latin Families' Strengths and Resilience Contribute to Their Well-Being*, National Research Center on Hispanic Children and Families, <https://www.hispanicresearchcenter.org/research-resources/latinx-families-strengths-and-resilience-contribute-to-their-well-being/>.

Hispanic Foursquare emphasizes strong Pentecostal ministry, praxis of the manifestations of the Spirit, and Spirit empowered leadership

According to the study *Renewalism and Hispanic Christianity* conducted by Pew Research,¹⁶ the influence of the Pentecostal movement among the Hispanic community is very high. Pentecostals are often defined as Evangelical Christians who are generally more committed to their faith than other Evangelical groups; they live their faith to the fullest, have witnessed miracles, and consider having a *vibrant* relationship with God as essential. Another Pew Research study says that of the 20% of Evangelical Hispanics in the U.S., 6.9% of them are Pentecostals, which is the largest segment;¹⁷ this includes Foursquare Hispanics, for whom fervent worship, the baptism of the Holy Spirit, and supernatural manifestations are inextricably part of their Christianity.

Pentecostalism among Hispanics has the potential for a dynamic future since there are many young Hispanics to carry it on. A survey shows that 46% of the Hispanic church's membership is between 30-49 years old.¹⁸ Many of these young adults are migrants from Latin American nations,¹⁹ where the rise of the Pentecostal church and praxis has steadily increased. This study also reflects the reality of the Hispanic Foursquare movement. Like its founder, the missionary spirit to all ethnic groups (Greek, πάντα τὰ ἔθνη [Matthew 28:19]) is still alive. Foursquare Hispanics are active in the U.S., seeking to reach not only

¹⁶ *The Shifting Religious Identify of Latinos in the United States*, Chapter 7: Renewalism and Hispanic Christianity, Pew Research Center, May 7, 2014, <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2014/05/07/chapter-7-renewalism-and-hispanic-christianity/>.

¹⁷ *Changing Faiths: Latinos and the Transformation of American Religion*, Pew Research, <https://www.pewresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/7/2007/04/>.

¹⁸ Roger G. Robins, *Pentecostals in the Evangelical Tradition Who Identify as Latino*, Pew Research Center, <https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/religious-landscape-study/racial-and-ethnic-composition/latino/religious-family/pentecostal-family-evangelical-trad/>.

¹⁹ According to a Pew Research study, nearly one in five Latin Americans now describe themselves as Protestant and, in all countries surveyed, most of them identify themselves as Pentecostal or belong to a Pentecostal denomination. David Masci, *Why Has Pentecostalism Grown So Dramatically in Latin America?* Pew Research, <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2014/11/14/why-has-pentecostalism-grown-so-dramatically-in-latin-america/>.

Hispanics, but also crossing cultural barriers. As David Masci asserts, the Pentecostal movement has become a global phenomenon.²⁰

Under the leadership of Sister McPherson, KFSG radio station was also used to reach the Spanish speaking masses with the Foursquare Gospel as early as 1924; this outreach increased in 1930 with Pastor Antonio Gamboa's radio outreach to Hispanics.²¹ Foursquare was among the earliest Christian organizations to own a Christian radio station in the U.S., with Hispanics having the opportunity to carry the Foursquare message in their native language over the airwaves. Today, many Hispanic pastors are making use of the media as McPherson did, and through this media, they are reaching thousands. This has allowed congregations to expand and grow, among first, second, and third-generation Hispanics. For example, Lifeway Research shows that 58% of the congregants of Hispanic churches are first generation, 24% of new church members are second generation, and 17% belong to the third generation of Hispanics.²² There is no doubt that using media to share the gospel has been a fruitful tool since 1924.

The message and praxis that attracted Hispanics to the Foursquare church has always been the Pentecostal ethos. Many of the fastest-growing Hispanic Foursquare congregations in Latin America attribute their growth to a strong Pentecostal ministry, praxis of the manifestations of the Spirit in the life of the local church, and Spirit-empowered leadership. Of late, some Foursquare Hispanic churches have become less passionate about Pentecostalism, but nevertheless, the majority of Foursquare Hispanics around the world are firm believers in the power of a revivalist spirit and the manifestation of signs and wonders. The *cruzadas de avivamiento* (“crusades or tent revival meetings”) were a part of Sister McPherson's ministry before Foursquare was founded,²³ and this has been a legacy continued by many Hispanic pastors in the U.S. and abroad.

²⁰ Masci, *Why Has Pentecostalism Grown So Dramatically in Latin America?*

²¹ *Foursquare Hispana, Part III*,

https://resources.foursquare.org/foursquare_hispana_part_3/.

²² Hispanic American Church Study, *A survey of pastors of Hispanic congregations in the U.S.*, Lifeway Research, 2022, <https://research.lifeway.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Hispanic-American-Church-Study-Report.pdf>.

²³ *Rolf K. McPherson Recalls His Mother's Tent Revivals*,

<https://resources.foursquare.org/rolf-k-mcpherson-recalls-his-mothers-tent-revivals/>.

Hispanic Foursquare is a community that values biblical-theological and leadership training

As we have seen, theological training has been a foundational element for the expansion of Foursquare. The former LIFE Bible College began offering Spanish classes early on, so that some of its students could plant Hispanic churches, go out into the Spanish speaking mission field, and not only evangelize but develop biblical-theological education and training for present and future leaders. A significant advance in Foursquare Hispanic theological education was the founding of two iconic schools: *Facultad de Teología* in Montebello, CA, and *Angelus Bible Institute* in Los Angeles. *Facultad* opened its doors in 1978 under the leadership of Foursquare Hispanic pastor, Dr. Enrique Zone. It is still in operation with a tremendous impact not only within the Foursquare church but interdenominationally. It offers programs in ministry training at the associate and bachelor levels. Many Foursquare Hispanics have also benefited from *Facultad's* bridge option into accredited graduate-level programs at several U.S. institutions. *Angelus Bible Institute* (ABI) was established in 1986 by Dr. Raymundo Díaz, who at the time was the lead Hispanic pastor at Angelus Temple. ABI is a Bible institute that offers a certificate in ministry and has expanded by having off-site extensions in other states and even other countries in Latin America.²⁴

The most recent and significant advancement in higher education for Foursquare Hispanics was the start of Hispanic Programs at Life Pacific University (LPU), Foursquare's flagship university in Southern California. In 2018, the university received a special donation to launch a Master of Arts in Leadership entirely in Spanish, marking the beginning of the Hispanic Programs Department at LPU. Dr. Daniel Ruarte was the founding director, pioneering the program and establishing the Hispanic department. To date, more than fifty students have graduated, and multiple cohorts are starting every year. Today, the department is under the leadership of Dr. Hugo Aldana Jr., and there are expectations of national and international expansions for a global impact.

Interestingly, in an interview that Justo González offered to Benjamin Wayman, Gonzalez stated that the challenges with Hispanic theological education are many.²⁵ However, he considers one of the

²⁴ Yader Parrales, *A Brief Timeline of the Foursquare Church and the Hispanic Movement* (Anaheim: Foursquare Missions Press, 2023), 16-17.

²⁵ Benjamin Wayman and Justo González, "Seminaries Need More Latinos," *Christianity Today*, November 13, 2020,

biggest challenges the fact that there are not enough qualified Hispanic faculty who are bilingual and bicultural for the existing demand in the U.S. In fact, many institutions that offer Hispanic-targeted theological education do so with non-Hispanic faculty, which is why González affirms that the crisis of theological education is not only financial but also demographic.

Life Pacific University's work in English and Spanish is a response to this problem. The formation of ministers was always on Sister McPherson's mind. *Facultad*, ABI, and LPU have been key in promoting theological education, leadership training, and the development of more qualified faculty. The Master of Arts in Leadership in Spanish has allowed several new Hispanic leaders to graduate and serve as faculty in Bible schools that prepare workers throughout the U.S. and the world.

The favor of God continues among Foursquare Hispanics. In 2022, LPU, together with Azusa Pacific University (APU) and Latin American Bible Institute (LABI), received a grant of five million dollars (1.4 was for Hispanic Programs at LPU) entitled, *Lilly Endowment Pathways for Tomorrow*. The project is for these three institutions to work together to expand theological and ministry training to Hispanics. Built on the slogan, "From certificate to doctorate," it will give Hispanic students a path to further biblical and theological education. The grant was so important that Hannah McClellan commented on it in her article in *Christianity Today*.²⁶

The mission of LIFE Bible College that Sister McPherson founded continues among Foursquare Hispanics because there are Foursquare Hispanic leaders who value education and training. As Hispanics, it is necessary to have an identity that allows us to deal with current challenges, buoyed by proper training to serve with excellence and stay current for future generations. LPU is an institution that provides high-quality education for Foursquare Hispanics, and we are grateful. Foursquare's Pentecostal-based doctrine and theological foundations must remain strong. Sister McPherson knew that anointing transforms people, but it is education and training that shapes them.

<https://www.christianitytoday.com/ct/2020/november-web-only/justo-gonzalez-los-seminarios-necesitan-mas-latinos-es.html>.

²⁶ Hannah McClellan, "Christian Schools Building 'Consortium' for Hispanic Theology Education," *Christianity Today*, November 23, 2022, <https://www.christianitytoday.com/news/2022/november/hispanic-theology-education-lilly-endowment-azusa-life-labi.html>.

Hispanic Foursquare is a community faithful to *las tradiciones* (traditions)

The Foursquare Hispanic community is the repository of an extraordinary denominational legacy. It can be said that today's Hispanic Foursquare church is the result of Sister McPherson's prayers and emphases. Two decades into the twenty-first century, with all its diversity, the Foursquare Hispanic community continues to embody the values of its founder, working hard to make the dream of impacting the world with the message of the Foursquare Gospel. We are committed to the words of her famous homily, "This is my task, this is my task, to take the gospel around the world."²⁷ It is a Foursquare tradition the Hispanic community ardently preserves.

Early Foursquare symbolism, culture, and traditions were very demonstrative and specific—the four-colored flag, symbolizing salvation (red), the baptism of the Holy Spirit (yellow), divine healing (blue), and the Coming King (purple); the symbols of the cross, the dove, the cup and the crown, which have similar understanding; and the four faces from Ezekiel: the face of the man who symbolizes Jesus crucified, the face of the lion representing Jesus as a baptizer with the Holy Spirit, the face of the ox, an animal that carries the heaviest burdens, typifying the fact that Jesus carries upon Himself the burdens of our pains and diseases, and the face of the eagle, which depicts Jesus as the Coming King. This is also Foursquare's defining verse: "Jesus Christ is the same yesterday and today and forever" (Hebrews 13:8, TNIV). All of these continue to hold meaning and significance among Foursquare Hispanics.²⁸

Conclusion

The Foursquare Hispanic community represents all Spanish-speaking peoples in Central, South, and North America, the Caribbean, Europe, and parts of Africa. If you consider all these areas, it may be one of the largest ethnic groups in our Foursquare family. It is a growing community within Foursquare that will continue to expand with great opportunities for the future. We conclude this article with four

²⁷ "Aimee Semple McPherson Classic Sermon: This is My Task," *Foursquare Leader* (Spring 2020), <https://resources.foursquare.org/audio/aimee-semple-mcphersons-classic-sermon-this-is-my-task/>.

²⁸ There are also the Keystones and Global Distinctives discussed in Friesen and Dunahoo's article.

emphases from Hispanic culture that, if embraced, will benefit the global Foursquare community going forward.

Cultivate a strong family atmosphere

Understanding that Foursquare Hispanics are a community who loves *la familia*, we feel it is very important that the denomination as an organization strive to be a family more than a company. Providing pastoral care for the credentialed ministers should be paramount to the movement; and Foursquare districts and leaders should cultivate family values and focus on the care and health of their pastors more than operations, issues, legalities, and events.

Promote Pentecostal ministry

Understanding that Foursquare Hispanics are a community that emphasizes strong Pentecostal ministry, praxis of the manifestations of the Spirit, and Spirit-empowered leadership, it is very important that the denomination as an organization strives to stand firm in its roots and better promote praxis models of healthy-Pentecostalism.²⁹ Today, there are churches of other denominational lines integrating elements of Pentecostalism into their services because they know the value it adds to the impact and transformation of people. In Foursquare, it should be promoted clearly and unreservedly with moderation, as did Sister McPherson.

Promote formal education and leadership training

Understanding that Foursquare Hispanics are a community that values biblical-theological and leadership training, it is very important that the denomination as an organization strives to promote formal education and leadership training. We believe that Foursquare leaders must be more involved in the operations of our Foursquare universities, Bible colleges, and schools of ministry, fostering the value of formal preparation for ministry, requiring basic biblical-theological pre-service training and ongoing educational development for ministers.

²⁹ The term, “Healthy Pentecostal Churches,” was developed by Dr. Ruarte and is a new perspective to try to define in a practical way what it means to have a church that actively and healthily practices biblical Pentecostalism and the quadrangular Pentecostal doctrine. We understand that there is much to write, research and explain about this and the Foursquare Hispanic community is committed to move the discussion forward.

Create Foursquare traditions to shape our culture

Understanding that Foursquare Hispanic are a community faithful to *las tradiciones* (traditions), it is very important that the denomination as an organization strives to create unique Foursquare traditions that foster a culture of its own. Traditions create culture, and culture directs behavior. Hispanics value clear traditions. Sister McPherson was a creator of traditions and culture, including uniforms, songs, slogans, a flag, a denominational verse, elements required in church ministries, etc. Everyone knew what being Foursquare meant. Creating new traditions without leaving aside some longstanding traditions is important. Who are we as Foursquare Hispanics? Who are we as Foursquare? Distinctives are important because they reveal how we see the world, but traditions are more important because they reveal who we are and how we walk in the world.

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